

Application of MobileNet Variant Model in Road Classification

Abstract—This paper reviews the applications and innovative approaches of deep learning based models for road classification in recent years, based on which a MobileNet variant model is proposed and designed, introducing the Squeeze Excitation (SE) module and cross-validation and as well as weight balancing on imbalanced datasets for the identification and analysis of road classification. The design of the MobileNet variant model is then explained in detail and the effectiveness of the introduced novel modules in improving the model performance and generalisation is experimentally verified, with conclusions and suggestions for improvement in future research directions. Finally, we developed a model-based web application.

I. INTRODUCTION

Road surface detection and classification have gained considerable attention in the domains of traffic safety and intelligent driving in recent years. Accurate detection of road surfaces and scenarios is crucial for driving safety. Factors such as the physical condition and structure of the road's surface can present challenges for driving equipment [1]. In addition to this, different road surfaces can cause different degrees of safety risks, where road surface anomalies due to waterlogging or wetness can affect the friction between the vehicle and the road surface, and are more likely to cause serious traffic accidents [2].

In the research of vision-based road surface classification, methods based on machine learning or deep learning have been applied in various ways. Among them, machine learning based methods involve various image processing techniques such as Jerman enhancement filter, Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), region of interest (ROI) extraction and so on [3]. These methods are employed to extract intricate properties from road images and are utilised in coordination with algorithms like KNN, SVM, and LGBM to classify various road conditions. However, machine learning-based techniques have limitations because their classification performance depends heavily on the feature extraction techniques used and the quality of the training data. Different datasets require targeted feature extraction techniques, while incorrect or inadequate feature extraction may have a huge impact on the classification performance.

Deep learning based methods have overcome the limitations of machine learning techniques that require manual design of features, deep learning models can automatically learn complex patterns and features in data through multi-layer structures, DNNs and CNNs are widely used in the field of pavement identification and have achieved considerable results [4]. However, while various deep learning models have been applied to comprehensive road surface identification and

classification, there is a lack of research on deep learning applications for road surface identification with water. Wet road surfaces pose a safety hazard for driving and a targeted challenge for classification applications based on deep learning models.

This study introduces a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model that utilises MobileNet as a base to efficiently capture visual properties while minimising computational resources. Besides, we introduced the Squeeze Excitation (SE) module to target the learning of complex features of wet road surfaces from different channels. Furthermore, we performed weight balancing for the imbalanced dataset and fine-tuned part of the model's structure to fit specific datasets and application scenarios.

Our proposed model provides a deep learning-based application case for classification scenarios of wet and waterlogged road surfaces. Although there is still room for the model to improve in performance, this study experimentally validates the potential of deep learning in specific road surface classification scenarios and provides a valuable reference for subsequent related research.

The remaining chapters of this study are organized into the following five sections: section 3 reviews the main applications and development of deep learning techniques in road surface classification scenarios, section 4 describes in detail the CNN model based on MobileNet and the SE model, section 5 describes the background of the dataset and details of the processing of the imbalance issue, and section 6 demonstrates the efficacy of the SE model, weight balancing, and model structure fine-tuning for specific classification tasks by conducting several comparison experiments with the baseline model, moreover section 7 describes the application of the web design. Finally, section 8 summarizes the results of this study and possible future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Figure 1 lists the methods that have been applied or innovated based on deep learning models in the field of road surface classification in recent years, focusing on three main areas: semantic segmentation and attention mechanisms, the application of pre-trained models, and data enhancement and activation function innovation.

A. *Semantic segmentation and attention mechanisms*

Qiao 's [5] team proposed a VGG16-based model for a specific road splash scenario and improved the model performance by introducing semantic segmentation and self-attention

Research Team	Proposed method	Performance	Application Scenarios
Qiao [5]	VGG16 + Semantic Segmentation + Self-Attention Mechanism	Intersection over Union of background = 99%	Road Surface Water Splashing Detection
Narit Hnoohom [4]	ResNet + SE	F1-score = 98.15%	General Road Surface Classification
Hiroya [6]	SSD + MobileNet	Accuracy = 95% Inference speed (ms) = 30.6	Road Surface Damage Detection
Wansik Choi[7]	DeepLabv3 + CycleGAN + Weight Balancing	F1-score = 93%	General Road Surface Classification
Cheng [8]	CNN + Gai-Relu	Accuracy = 94.89%	General Road Surface Classification

Fig. 1.

mechanisms. Specifically, the authors' team captures the complex features of splash images at different levels by means of a self-invented encoder-decoder structure. In addition to this, the Splashed Water Attention Module (SWAM), which is based on a self-attention mechanism, is introduced to focus on key areas to further improve the recognition performance for specific scenes. Despite the excellent recognition performance of its model in critical regions, the semantic segmentation and self-attention mechanisms are a great challenge to computational resources and efficiency. In contrast, Narit Hnoohom [4] also introduced an effective attention mechanism based on deep learning models, the SE module, which allows the model to learn image features through different channels. The team's model has achieved very impressive performance on general road classification, however its potential for classification of waterlogged or other special types of road surfaces has not yet been fully demonstrated.

B. The application of pre-trained models

The models proposed by Narit Hnoohom [4] and Qiao [5] are applied to innovate in specific road surface recognition domains based on image features learned from pre-trained models ResNet and VGG16 respectively, and the effectiveness of the pre-trained models used by them are validated by experiments. In addition to this, the team of Hiroya [6] used MobileNet as a feature extractor in conjunction with the SSD model and demonstrated improved performance in experiments on road damage detection. While pre-trained models can improve feature recognition performance to some extent, they may also impose a certain computing burden, as in the case of ResNet and VGG16. By contrast, MobileNet's lightweight architecture has advantages in terms of computational efficiency. However, its effectiveness in specific application scenarios remains to be further verified.

C. Data enhancement and activation function innovation

In addition to the model itself, data processing and loss function optimization techniques in specific application scenarios are also of interest. For example, Cheng's [8] team adapted the ReLU function in their proposed CNN-based road surface classification method by introducing a nonlinear term and adjustable parameters to improve the model's performance

for nonlinearly differentiable data. However, optimization for the activation function may rely on certain mathematical understanding and validation, which poses certain challenges for research. In the context of data enhancement, the team led by Wansik Choi [7] employed the CycleGAN technique on the dataset to address the issue of data imbalance. They achieved this by transforming the dry pavement into other types of road surfaces. Also, its team used Median Frequency Balancing to calculate the class weights at the loss of cross-entropy, allowing the model to allocate attention according to the weights during the training process, further alleviating the data imbalance issue. Similar data processing methods are important references in application scenarios such as the road surface classification, where the quality and quantity of the data set have a significant impact. Therefore, based on the above analysis and comparison, this study will introduce the SE module based on MobileNet and propose a road classification model for waterlogged or wet road surfaces by weight balancing and structural fine-tuning, taking into account the arithmetic and resource limitations.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

A. Model design

In the initial research stage, we conducted in-depth research on the ResNet residual network [9]. This architecture has received widespread attention because of its powerful feature extraction capabilities and its breakthrough contributions in the field of deep learning. In particular, residual networks overcome the vanishing gradient problem in deep neural network training by introducing skip connections. Mathematically, if the input is x and the mapping is $F(x)$, then the output of the residual block

$$x + F(x) \quad (1)$$

Such a design can not be affected by the gradient becoming smaller in the middle layer. At the same time, the skip connection allows features to be directly propagated across some layers without being affected by the gradient becoming smaller in the deep network. As shown in the following Figure2.

Fig. 2. Squeeze-and-excitation block.

However, after in-depth analysis of our computing resources and project requirements, although we realized that the ResNet architecture is very effective for complex vision tasks, its high model complexity and computational cost are not suitable

for our constrained hardware environment and requirements for efficiency, so we turned to study the MobileNet model [?]. MobileNet and ResNet are two popular convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures. Compared with ResNet, MobileNet is more suitable for running on devices with limited computing power. A lightweight deep learning model, and MobileNet is easy to fine-tune with pre-trained weights. These are the two main reasons why we chose MobileNet as our infrastructure.

To avoid facing intellectual property related issues, we propose a variant model based on MobileNet to distinguish and identify various surfaces of roads. In this model, MobileNet is used as the feature extractor, and the top classifier of the original MobileNet is removed by setting `include_top=False`, and a custom layer is added for this task, and then a global average pooling layer, a Dropout layer, and two fully connected layers with ReLU activation function, and L1_L2 regularization is applied (`l1_l2=0.001`), and the Dense layer is used as the output layer. This layer has 3 neurons and softmax activation function, which is used for the three classifications task of this paper.

The model is compiled using the Adam optimizer, the loss function uses `sparse_categorical_crossentropy`, and accuracy is selected as the indicator for performance evaluation. At the same time, an early stopping strategy is added, with `val_loss` as the monitoring target and `patience=3`, to prevent overfitting and ensure that the model stops training and returns to the best performance state when the performance on the validation set no longer improves. In addition to the above designs, we have added several novel methods in order to improve model performance and generalization capabilities.

1) Squeeze-and-excitation block:

Squeeze-and-excitation block is a channel attention mechanism (SE Block) [10], which improves model performance by explicitly modeling the inter-channel dependencies of convolutional features. It is implemented with two key operations, compression and excitation. In this article, we add the SE block to the convolutional layer to enhance the expression. The SE module designed in this article is as shown below Figure3.

2) Application of cross-validation on the number of neurons:

Traditionally, cross-validation techniques select hyperparameters or evaluate model performance by dividing the data set into multiple smaller subsets and iteratively training and validating the model on the subsets. However, here, we extend the scope of cross-validation and apply it to structural decisions of MobileNet variant models. Specifically, the cross-validation method is used to optimize the number of neurons in the middle layer to replace the empirical value, thereby helping to determine the architectural design of the neural network, thereby improving the generalization ability and performance of the model, and finally determining the two middle layers. The number of neurons is 512, 256.

Fig. 3. Squeeze-and-excitation block.

B. Proposed model result

Model training is performed based on the above model design, and the results are as follow Figure4.

Fig. 4. training and Validation Loss - MobileNet variant model.

The training loss decreases rapidly initially and then stabilizes at a lower level. The validation loss remains relatively stable and low throughout the training process. We believe this indicates that the model learned well on the training set and maintains consistent performance on unseen validation data, which is a sign of good generalization ability of the model.

TABLE I
MODEL ACCURACY.

Category	Train	Valid	Test
Accuracy	72%	73%	70%

It can be seen from the TableI that the training set accuracy is 72%, the validation set accuracy is 73%, and the test set accuracy is 70%. From the test set confusion matrix TableII, the precision of `water_asphalt_severe` is 84%, the

TABLE II
TEST SET CONFUSION MATRIX.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	84%	64%	73%	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	59%	71%	64%	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	72%	74%	73%	800
<i>accuracy</i>			70%	2400
<i>macro avg</i>	72%	70%	70%	2400
<i>weight avg</i>	72%	70%	70%	2400

recall is 64%, and the F1-score is 73%. The precision of *water_concrete_severe* is 59%, the recall is 71%, the F1-score is 64%, and the precision of *water_gravel* is 72%, and the recall is 74%, and F1-score is 73%. The overall accuracy is 70%, the precision of macro avg and weight avg is 72%, the recall rate and F1-score is 70%.

In summary, in the test set and validation set, the accuracy of the model exceeds 70%. However, the accuracy in the test set drops, but not much. Considering comprehensive considerations, it is reasonable. The indicators of the confusion matrix show that the model has a high accuracy in the *water_asphalt_severe* category, but shows balanced performance in macro avg and weight avg, which echoes our application of algorithm-level data balancing methods. In addition, the hyperparameters applied in our current model are based on empirical judgments. We will adjust the hyperparameters in the future to further improve the model performance and generalization ability.

IV. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The data used in this article comes from a data set named *Group_4_water_severe* provided by Dr. Ihsan. This data set has been divided into training set, validation set, and test set. Each data set includes three types of road images, the categories are *water_asphalt_severe*, *water_concrete_severe* and *water_gravel*, and the image scale is 224×360 . The following is the information obtained during early data exploration:

TABLE III
SAMPLE DATASET DISTRIBUTION ACROSS DIFFERENT SETS.

Category	Train	Valid	Test
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	2581	250	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	5702	820	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	6422	820	800
Total	14705	1890	2400

^aThe dataset is provided by the Dr.Ihsan

TABLE IV
PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION ACROSS DIFFERENT SETS.

Category	Train	Valid	Test
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	18%	13%	33%
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	39%	44%	33%
<i>water_gravel</i>	43%	43%	34%

^aThe dataset is provided by the Dr.Ihsan

From TableIII and TableIV, we can see that the distribution of the three categories in the test set is more even. The

distribution of the three categories in the training set and the validation set are close. In particular, the *water_asphalt_severe* category accounts for only 18% (train) and 13% (valid), which is the same as the test set. The proportion of concentration 33% varies greatly, so solving the category imbalance problem is one of the challenges we face.

In data pre-processing, in order to solve the problem of category imbalance, we introduced the innovative method of weighting categories [10], which does not directly change the distribution of the data set, but adds category weights to the algorithm to alleviate category imbalance. The impact is to assign different importance weights to samples of different categories during training. However, since the *water_asphalt_severe* category in the training set and validation set is very different from its proportion in the test set, and the model will learn the bias of the category weights instead of learning the intrinsic differences of the categories from a more balanced data perspective, the introduction of category weights may affect the generalization ability of the model, and there is the possibility of future improvement.

In addition to facing the challenge of class imbalance, we have also made certain integration innovations in data enhancement methods. In addition to applying conventional enhancement methods such as random left and right, flipping up and down, brightness, and contrast, we also added adjustments to hue and saturation, so that it can be better identified. In addition, we also performed conventional image pre-processing, such as decoding images, resizing images, normalizing, label encoding, and batch processing steps.

V. EXPERIMENTS/RESULTS & ANALYSIS

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the innovative modules studied in this article in improving the performance of deep learning models, we adopted a paper-based approach out of consideration for rigor, experimental comparability, and persuasiveness. That is, a model in the replicated paper is used as a reference benchmark. By comparing the replicated model with the model integrating the innovative module on the same data set, the impact of the innovative module on model performance and generalization ability is quantitatively analyzed.

However, it is important to note that when introducing new modules, performance does not always improve as we would expect. There may be model overfitting, improper parameter configuration, or other unknown situations, so effectiveness comparison needs to be viewed dialectically.

Reproduction model reference [11]. The model adopts CNN architecture and starts with three convolutional layers. After each convolutional layer, a maximum pooling layer and a batch normalization layer are set. The first convolutional layer has 32 filters and the filter size is 3×3 , the activation function uses ReLU, and L2 regularization (rate 0.001) is introduced. The following two convolutional layers increase the number of filters to 64 and 128 respectively. The filter size remains unchanged. ReLU is also used as the activation function and L2 regularization. After the convolution and

pooling layers, the model adds a flattening layer and then adds a fully connected layer with 256 neurons, still using ReLU as the activation function. At the same time, a Dropout layer with a Dropout rate of 0.5 is introduced to further reduce overfitting, and the fully connected layer uses softmax as the activation function. Model compilation uses the Adam optimizer, the loss function is set to categorical_crossentropy, and the performance evaluation select accuracy and confusion matrix.

A. Novel module verification

This part of the experiment is conducted on the Windows 11 operating system, using Radeon 780M Graphics GPU. The execution environment is Python 3.11.5, which relies on TensorFlow 2.15.0. The parameter settings of the experimental model include the default parameters of the learning rate, the batch size is 32, the number of training iterations is 50, L2 regularization (L2 rate 0.001) is used, and settings Early stopping mechanism (patience is 3).

Fig. 5. Squeeze-and-excitation block.

Figure5 shows the difference in training and verification losses between the recurring model and the recurring model and the novel module. We can find that the recurring model has overfitting, but after adding the novel module, both the training loss and the verification loss decrease. , the performance model performs well on both the training set and the validation set, and the model with the cross validation module has slight fluctuations in the validation loss during the training process. It seems that the method of adjusting category weights and SE Block is healthier, and the gap between training loss and validation loss is small. Adjusting class weights assigns different weights to different classes, which encourages the model to pay more attention to classes with fewer samples. SE Block also enhances feature expression and helps the model focus on important features. Both methods therefore generalize better to all categories, thereby reducing the risk of overfitting. However, the application of cross-validation on neurons more changes the performance of the current fully connected layer,

which is related to the design of the fully connected layer in the model. Therefore, we can only say that the application of cross-validation on neurons has limited ability to improve the performance of the currently designed MobileNet variant model, and it is difficult to evaluate whether it is useless for other models.

TABLE V
THE PERFORMANCE OF REPRODUCTION MODEL.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	89%	36%	51%	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	48%	79%	60%	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	63%	62%	62%	800
<i>accuracy</i>			59%	2400
<i>macro avg</i>	67%	59%	58%	2400
<i>weight avg</i>	67%	59%	58%	2400

TABLE VI
THE PERFORMANCE OF REPRODUCTION MODEL WITH CLASS WEIGHT.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	66%	67%	67%	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	51%	59%	55%	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	63%	53%	58%	800
<i>accuracy</i>			60%	2400
<i>macro avg</i>	60%	60%	60%	2400
<i>weight avg</i>	60%	60%	60%	2400

TABLE VII
THE PERFORMANCE OF REPRODUCTION MODEL WITH SE BLOCK.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	73%	57%	64%	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	52%	72%	60%	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	69%	57%	63%	800
<i>accuracy</i>			62%	2400
<i>macro avg</i>	64%	62%	62%	2400
<i>weight avg</i>	64%	62%	62%	2400

TABLE VIII
THE PERFORMANCE OF REPRODUCTION MODEL WITH CROSS VALIDATION.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>water_asphalt_severe</i>	57%	79%	67%	800
<i>water_concrete_severe</i>	55%	43%	48%	800
<i>water_gravel</i>	66%	55%	60%	800
<i>accuracy</i>			59%	2400
<i>macro avg</i>	59%	59%	58%	2400
<i>weight avg</i>	59%	59%	58%	2400

From TableV, TableVI, TableVII, TableIX show the performance indicators of the recurrence model as a baseline for comparison with other recurrence models that add novel modules.

We can see the accuracy of the reproduction model is 59%, the accuracy of the reproduction model with SE Block is 62%, the accuracy of the reproduction model with class weight is 60%, the accuracy of the reproduction model with cross

validation is 59%. After the introduction of the SE module, the accuracy and F1-score increased by 3%, and the recall and F1-score indicators became more balanced. It shows that introducing the SE module in the decision-making process of classification tasks can improve the overall performance of the model. After the introduction of class weight, although there is no good performance in overall indicators such as accuracy, however, in the water_asphalt_severe category, in addition to decrease 23% in precision, but 21% increase in recall, and 16% increase in F1-score, it shows that classification is performed when the data is unbalanced increasing the weight can indeed improve the sensitivity of the model in identifying certain feature categories, but it will also lead to a decrease in accuracy. After introducing cross validation after applying it to neurons, since the cross validation in this experiment is applied to the fully connected layer, Although it can be find that there is no change in the overall performance, but the recall rate in the water_asphalt_severe category is significantly increased by 43%, and the F1-score is increased by 16%, indicating that although there is no adjustment of category weights, the number of fully connected layer neurons of the most suitable model is obtained. It improves the ability to identify positive samples and also enhances the generalization ability of the model.

B. Analysis of model hyperparameter results

TABLE IX
HYPERPARAMETER COMBINATION PERFORMANCE OF MOBILENET
VARIANT MODEL.

Hyperparameter combination	Train set accuracy	Test set accuracy
<i>lr=0.01, epochs=10</i>	72%	68%
<i>lr=0.01, epochs=20</i>	71%	64%
<i>lr=0.01, epochs=30</i>	73%	68%
<i>lr=0.001, epochs=10</i>	75%	69%
<i>lr=0.001, epochs=20</i>	76%	69%
<i>lr=0.001, epochs=30</i>	76%	70%
<i>lr=0.0001, epochs=10</i>	72%	66%
<i>lr=0.0001, epochs=20</i>	71%	65%
<i>lr=0.0001, epochs=30</i>	74%	69%

From the tableIX, the accuracy performance is good when the hyperparameter combination is $lr=0.001$, $epochs=30$. This may be one of the best hyperparameter combinations, especially from the perspective of model generalization.

The performance of hyperparameter combinations with $lr=0.001$ is very well on the test set. Especially when epochs is 20 and 30, the test set accuracy is 69% and 70% respectively, which also confirms the lower lr . It allows the model to learn more general features, especially as the epochs increase, it may perform better. However, it should be noted that the overfitting can be solved by early stopping.

As the epochs increase, when lr is 0.001 or 0.0001, the accuracy of the test set improves, indicating that a lower lr while increasing the epochs can improve the performance of the model. However, when the $lr=0.01$, we can find that despite increasing the number of training rounds, the accuracy of the test set has decreased. This may be due to the learning rate being too high.

To sum up, adjusting the learning rate and training rounds can improve the generalization ability of the model to a certain extent. In terms of hyperparameter adjustment methods, lower learning rates and increasing training rounds are a very good strategy. Limited by current computing resources, the MobileNet variant model still has a lot of room for improvement in hyperparameter adjustment. When more computing resources are available, more hyperparameters can be added for adjustment to improve the generalization of the model ability.

VI. INTRODUCTION TO THE WEB APPLICATION

In this study, we have developed an interactive web application based on the proposed model for practical application purposes. Specifically, the web application builds a front-end user interface through HTML, CSS and JavaScript, and a back-end framework based on flask, realizing front-end and back-end asynchronous communication through Ajax, so that the user can access the road classification results through an intuitive web page to enhance the comprehensibility and practicality of the model.

This study provides a simple and intuitive front-end layout as shown in Figure6. Users can upload up to five images at a time for categorization via the "Upload" button located at the bottom left, and the classification results will be displayed in the bottom output window in the form of "File Name - Prediction Result". In addition, the right side of the layout shows the schematic diagrams and explanatory texts of 3 different wet or waterlogged road surfaces to help users better understand the road surface classification results.

Fig. 6. Squeeze-and-excitation block.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the application of SE module, the application of cross-validation of the number of neurons, and the method of using class weight to deal with the data imbalance technique on the basis of the pre-training model MobileNet has achieved some degree of results, but it can still be improved in the next few directions in the future research.

Incorporating additional feature extraction techniques on the basis of the MobileNet variant to enhance feature representation within the model, thereby improving the model's

ability to recognize road features and enhance overall model performance.

The application of cross-validation on the fully connected layers has improved the model's capability to correctly identify positive samples. Future research could extend this approach to other layers, such as the number of kernels in pooling layers to further enhance model performance.

The use of class weights has improved the representation of specific categories within the model, although, as mentioned in this paper, it can lead to a decrease in precision for those categories. Future efforts could focus on improving data balancing based on class weights.

Employing more systematic hyperparameter optimization techniques, such as grid search, random search, or Bayesian optimization, to identify the optimal configuration of model parameters.

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